

EFFECT OF H⁺ IONS ON THE LUMINESCENT PROPERTIES OF GASE SINGLE CRYSTAL

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Abstract. *The excitation and photoluminescence (PL) spectra of a GaSe single crystal irradiated with H⁺ ions with an energy of 70 keV were studied in the temperature range of 20÷300 K. It was found that the energetic state of the maximum observed at a wavelength of ~622 nm in the PL spectra does not depend on the excitation energy and radiation dose. Since point defects (Frenkel pairs) formed in the crystal lattice as a result of the action of H⁺ ions ($1 \cdot 10^{15}$ - $5 \cdot 10^{15}$ cm⁻³) partially compensate for structural defects, the intensity of PL radiation I increases ~5 times. The increase in the intensity of the PL - band at low radiation doses is a result of recombination radiation occurring as a result of the interaction of acceptor and donor-type point defects formed in the crystal lattice.*

Keywords: *GaSe, photoluminescence, H⁺ ions, photoconductivity.*

Gallium selenide (GaSe) is a semiconductor material and its luminescent properties are the subject of extensive research. The luminescence properties of GaSe undergo dynamic changes under the influence of H⁺ ions with an energy of 70 keV. These results open up new opportunities for applications of GaSe in optoelectronics. The effect of H⁺ ions allows GaSe to be used in radiation detectors and other optoelectronic devices. These devices can measure the energy of γ rays and provide a corresponding signal, thus increasing the effect of H⁺ ions on the luminescence properties and the radiation measurement capability of the material. [1,2]

The aim of the work is to study defects in the crystal and investigate the effect of H⁺ ions on the photoluminescence properties of GaSe crystal in the temperature range of 20÷300 K. These defects can play a crucial role in the operation of devices used in technological fields and can not only reduce the internal quantum efficiency, but also make it impossible to generate light. In addition, some scattering centers may form due to defects, which leads to a decrease in carrier mobility.

The studied GaSe single crystals with p-type conductivity were obtained by the Bridgman-Stockbarger method [3,4]. The equilibrium concentrations of charge carriers and traps in GaSe crystals were calculated and $n_0 \sim$ were $2.8 \cdot 10^{10}$ cm⁻³ and $8.2 \cdot 10^{15}$ cm⁻³, respectively. The emission of the samples was excited by laser beams at wavelengths of 532 nm (Nd:YAG) and 325 nm (HeCd). PL spectra of GaSe samples were measured under excitation with monochromatic radiation. A xenon source and a 605 nm filter were used for the photoluminescence measurements for a selected emission wavelength of 622 nm. The pre-excitation and PL spectra of H⁺ ions of a GaSe single crystal were studied using a Nd:YAG laser (355 nm) (Figure 1). The excitation spectrum consists of broad bands of high intensity located in the range of 450-605 nm. The high intensity peak observed in the spectrum corresponds to 498 nm, and the other two weak intensity peaks correspond to 528 and 566 nm, respectively. (Figure 1. curve 1). It was found that the PL spectrum with a maximum at 622 nm is observed in the wavelength range of 558-668 nm. The emission maximum observed with a maximum of 622 nm is due to interband radiative

recombination, which is in complete agreement with the results obtained in the work [4].

Figure 1. Excitation (1), photoluminescence (2), and photoluminescence reflection spectra (2') of a GaSe single crystal at 300 K.

When a GaSe crystal is excited with a source with a wavelength corresponding to the peaks observed in the excitation spectrum, the energetic state of the 622nm peak observed in the PL spectrum does not change and does not affect the shape and position of the maxima of the PL spectrum. The observed characteristics indicate that the GaSe crystal has stability indicators as a phosphor, and the observed PL spectrum covers the wavelength range from 558 nm to 668 nm. The maximum of the PL spectrum corresponds to 622 nm, and this compound has intense radiation in the red region of the light wavelength Fig. 1, curve 2).

In the present study, the effect of H^+ ions on the photoluminescence emission of a GaSe crystal was investigated. Irradiation of the samples with H^+ ions ($1 \cdot 10^{15}$ - $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) was carried out at $T=300 \text{ K}$. It was found that the wavelength corresponding to the maximum observed at 622 nm before irradiation and the shape of the PL spectrum were independent of the absorbed dose. However, under the influence of radiation, the intensity of the spectra increases (~ 5 times) and the half-width broadens. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. PL spectra of a GaSe single crystal previously exposed to H^+ ions at 300 K: 1.- 0 ; 2- $5 \cdot 10^{15}$; 3- $1 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-2}$

Analysis of the results shows that the interaction of point defects formed in the GaSe crystal due to the action of H^+ ions with structural defects in the crystal leads to the ordering of the defects, and the intensity of the peak in the PL spectrum increases due to the increase in the intensity of the recombination radiation. Thus, since radiation defects formed during irradiation partially compensate for structural defects, they reduce the concentration of centers that act as trapping centers for photoexcited charge carriers. This increases the recombination process of charge carriers and ultimately leads to an increase in the intensity of the peak corresponding to the maximum in the PL spectrum of the crystal.

The luminescence band observed at a wavelength of 0.622 nm in the PL spectrum of the p-GaSe crystal is due to recombination radiation occurring in specific defects (Ga^+, Se^-) in the crystal lattice. The fact that the intensity and energy level of the PL - band do not depend on the nature of the excitation spectrum indicates that defects of an acceptor nature predominate during the acceptor-donor interaction. The Stokes shift was determined based on the difference in energies corresponding to the maxima of the absorption and emission spectra and was $\Delta S = 0.12$ eV. Based on Mott's law, the activation energy of the thermal quenching process of radiation intensity was determined ($E_a = 27$ meV).

Analysis of the above results shows that due to the interaction of radiation defects formed in the GaSe crystal as a result of the impact of low-energy (70 keV) H^+ ions with irregularities in the crystal lattice (structural defects), the defects are ordered, and as a result, recombination radiation is observed [1]. Thus, since the defects formed during irradiation partially compensate for the structural defects, they reduce the concentration of trapping centers for photoexcited charge carriers. This causes an increase in the intensity of the peak corresponding to the maximum in the PL spectrum of the crystal. The radiation intensity increases exponentially with the increase in radiation dose from $5 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ to $2 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The corresponding result is consistent with the results obtained in studies [5].

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